

How CoPs are formed and sustained around Open Source Ecosystems

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Introduction

Communities of practice are formed when groups of individuals come together over shared interests, have comparable levels of domain knowledge or expertise, and interact often enough to develop a shared understanding of challenges and opportunities (Wenger 2000). The formation and maintenance of CoPs in the context of scientific open source are similar to how CoPs originate in other stem communities. In this report, I describe how code becomes an open-source product and eventually undergoes a transformation into an open-source ecosystem, the conditions necessary for such a transformation, and how such communities are sustained over time.

Open-Source Ecosystems (OSE)

A working definition for an Open Source Ecosystem (OSE) as per the US National Science Foundation (National Science Foundation 2022) is a *self-sustaining organization that enables the ongoing collaborative, asynchronous development of an open-source product that is designed to be publicly accessible, modifiable, and distributable by anyone under an open-source licensing model*. Further, for this type of organization to remain sustainable, *it must be governed by sociotechnical processes and mechanisms for continuous development, integration, and deployment, and sustained by a decentralized and open network of contributors who contribute their time and expertise to develop and maintain the open-source product.*"

As OSEs are a broad category, I limit my discussion to scientific or research-oriented OSEs to remain within the scope of the CSID work. In this space, ideas for open-source software typically originate as part of analyses associated with research papers/projects. While most such *analysis code* is never visible to anyone outside the team, a subset of such code, especially novel methods, gets captured as *prototype research software*. These are typically minimum viable software made available through GitHub or other source control platforms. The characteristics that make the prototype software are that they have limited documentation and testing and have not been explicitly engineered for speed or stability. The primary purpose of making them

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available as installable units of code is to get community feedback and buy-in from domain researchers. Some of these tools then find substantial product-market fit and enter the *research software infrastructure* space, either by being folded into upstream work or by growing a community around it. The question of long-term sustainability enters the conversation at this stage as there is no expectation of analysis code or prototype software to be sustained. Whatever artifact that exists at this stage is still very much an open-source product, where artifacts such as software, models, and methods are released publicly, but still have to undergo a transformation into an ecosystem. The key to this transformation is growing a community of practice around the product.

CoPs enable the transformation from an open-source product to an ecosystem

Ad-hoc to formal community building: The act of finding a product-market fit for prototype software is also the stage where researchers come together over a common interest or problem. For many scientific OSEs, community-building efforts at this stage are ad-hoc without any intentional efforts or programs to provide pathways to engagement. With the rise in funding opportunities for scientific OSS projects over the past decade (examples include, The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation's [Better Software For Science program](#), [Moore Foundation's Data-Driven Discovery \(DDD\)](#), [CZI's Essentials of Open Source for Science](#), etc), this is also the stage where many communities seek their first round of funding. Armed with evidence that there is interest in the tool, founders typically seek dedicated funding for growing the community and/or advancing technical developments.

Product engagement versus community engagement: The act of finding a product-market fit, what the product can do for a potential user, is different than community engagement, which is the act of facilitating interactions between and among individuals in the community to do things with the product that they would not be able to do individually. This process of community building has been greatly improved and facilitated by the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement through their Community Engagement Fellows (CEF) program (Woodley and Pratt 2020). A large majority of scientific open source projects that are affiliated with fiscal sponsors such as NumFocus, CS&S, and Community Initiatives have had at least one member (usually a dedicated community manager) go through this course and map out the community and pathways to engagement.

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Defining community by naming a shared purpose: As previously described in the report about [rOpenSci as a CoP](#), communities need to have a clearly defined domain of focus, a healthy mix of practitioners at different skill levels, and activities to support such an audience to qualify as a CoP. But even before that process begins, projects need to identify one or more shared goals, ones that cannot be accomplished by any single entity. Community members also need to feel a sense of belonging, the ability to shape the culture, and where they feel empowered to lead an activity. CSCCE defines these four elements as purpose, culture, belonging, and power.

Various modes of engagement within a community: Once communities are seeded, a good lens through which to view growth and engagement is the community participation model. The five modes are: convey/consume, contribute, collaborate, co-cocreate, and champion (Woodley and Pratt 2020). These are not a linear progression and various modes can co-exist at any time. Projects that are in the process of transforming into an ecosystem typically only have one or two modes like convey/consume (disseminating their products) and contribute (accepting feedback, bug requests, etc). Stepping into a more complex mode of collaboration such as co-creation requires power sharing and trust and this is where many scientific open-source projects fail. When founders refuse to give up control, or a funding imbalance leads to one stakeholder operating by fiat, co-creation is not possible and community members may exit to other CoPs.

Opportunities: When establishing new CoPs in the CSID community, being aware of the various conditions necessary for the existence of a sustainable OSE can be the difference between success and failure. The critical component appears to be the creation of conditions that allow for projects to move away from founder-led control as it grows. A telltale sign that a mature community is not sustainable is when there are no clear pathways to leadership. Pathways to leadership include starting off as a user, making a contribution, and then graduating to a maintainer. This path occurs not just in code/software contributions, but also as working group/area leads, such as in the context of peer review (author → reviewer → editor) and any other area of work in a project. In the elected board model, community members that meet

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a level of service criteria can become eligible to run for the board or steering committee.

References

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